

OpenCitations for SSH: Improving OPERAS Metrics and Enriching Knowledge Graphs

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Objective

This paper aims to highlight the significance of extracting citation data from publications in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) within the context of the GRAPHIA and LUMEN projects. It explains how these efforts support the broader mission of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure and enhance the OpenCitations infrastructure. These projects seek to address the issue of “missing references” in SSH literature, as emphasized by David Shotton, by leveraging the expertise and services of OpenCitations (Peroni & Shotton, 2020).

The GRAPHIA and LUMEN projects aim to transform practices and collaborative processes across scientific domains. GRAPHIA focuses on building infrastructure for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), including the SSH Knowledge Graph (SSH KG), the SSH Citation Index, and the development of AI tools to support SSH data analysis. Meanwhile, LUMEN seeks to expand the functionality of the GoTriple platform—which has proven to be a cutting-edge solution for the SSH community—and to establish interoperability between different scientific fields, such as mathematics, Earth sciences, and molecular dynamics, by developing a multi-domain resource discovery platform.

As a leading research infrastructure in SSH, OPERAS serves as the coordinator of the GRAPHIA project and actively participates in LUMEN. Both projects aim to support open scholarly communication in SSH by increasing the visibility, accessibility, and interoperability of research data. In particular, citation data extraction is crucial for addressing the issue of “missing references” in SSH literature, supporting responsible research evaluation, and improving metadata quality. Leveraging the OpenCitations infrastructure provides a strong foundation for these initiatives, aligning with the goals of both projects.

Methods and material: extracting citations with CEX

The OpenCitations infrastructure includes a component, called CEX, able to perform automatic annotation of in-text citations in academic papers provided in PDF, freely available on GitHub (<https://github.com/opencitations/cec>). There are several toolkits that perform the same task with accurate results. A recent and exhaustive comparison can be found in (Backes et al. 2024).

CEX aims at improving the state-of-the-art by also adding rich annotations for each reference, and exporting them in RDF so as to be interoperable and integrated with other datasets. Each input PDF file is processed and converted in a structured output in TEI-XML format, that contains annotations over the extracted bibliographic references. From that output, a JSON file containing the citations' sentences and the name of the section in which each in-text reference pointer appears is created. The sections' titles might be helpful for further analysis on the citations, for instance on their function and relation with other citations. Indeed, the tool offers the possibility to align the sections' headings with those that conform to the Discourse Element Ontology (DEO) (Constantin et al. 2016), exploiting the spaCy function to predict semantic similarity.

CEX utilizes GROBID (Lopez 2009), a machine learning library designed to extract, parse, and restructure raw documents into structured XML/TEI-encoded documents. Thanks to its modular design, GROBID allows for independent training of various models based on specific requirements. Currently, CEX utilizes GROBID's citation model, which has been trained using Training 5—one of six available configurations (Pagnotta 2024). The ongoing focus is on enhancing performance by training both the segmentation and full-text models of GROBID. The current implementation achieves very good results, with a f1-score of 0.8191.

The development of CEX can be divided into three phases. The predefined GROBID model was initially trained using a particular configuration (Pagnotta 2024) and collection of manually annotated documents.

The training set has been extended, together with the development of new modules for enrichment and RDF export, in order to achieve better results and to evaluate them systematically. This is an ongoing activity within the EU-funded GraspOS project (<https://graspos.eu/>), whose goal is to build a research assessment infrastructure to promote Open Science infraResearch Assessment to Promote Open Science. The toolkit will be further improved during the GRAPHIA project along different directions, among which: (i) more precise extraction of reference components and from images and complex texts (ii) disambiguation of the cited publication; (iii) citation classifications and (iv) integration with other Linked Open Data sources compliant to the OpenCitations Data Model. In particular, we plan to explore LLMs to perform these tasks or part of them, in combination with existing approaches, for instance those based on GROBID.

Expected Outcomes and Value Proposition

The GRAPHIA and LUMEN projects utilize OpenCitations infrastructure and services to improve the visibility, accessibility, and usability of citation data in SSH. These efforts will directly contribute to the OPERAS Metrics Service and SSH Knowledge Graph (SSH KG), as well as the wider SSH community.

Contribution to OPERAS Metrics Service. OPERAS Metrics Service aims to provide citation-based metrics essential for assessing the impact of publications and authors in SSH. Data from OpenCitations serve as a robust foundation for these metrics, aligning with OPERAS's mission to promote open science. Through the GRAPHIA and LUMEN projects, OPERAS Metrics Service will be enriched with citation data extracted using AI tools, expanding the scope and quality of available metrics. The service will offer insights into publication usage, including views, downloads, and open access availability, to encourage best practice in research evaluation.

Contribution to SSH Knowledge Graph (SSH KG). The GRAPHIA project aims to develop the SSH Knowledge Graph (SSH KG) as a central repository of SSH data. Citation data extracted from the project will form an integral part of SSH KG, strengthening connections between publications and enabling better knowledge discovery. The SSH Citation Extractor, enhanced within GRAPHIA, will provide high-quality citation data obtained using advanced AI methods. This will enable the automatic extraction of references from various sources, their parsing, disambiguation, enrichment with citation contexts, and classification of citation intents. The integration of citation data into SSH KG will improve interoperability and facilitate access to research resources in SSH, enabling a deeper understanding of complex relationships between publications.

New Applications of OpenCitations for the SSH Community. The GRAPHIA and LUMEN projects contribute to the development of an open citation index for SSH, leveraging OpenCitations' expertise and infrastructure. This is crucial in addressing the issue of “missing references” in SSH literature (Colavizza et al. 2023). The use of AI tools to automate citation extraction and data enrichment represents a novel approach in this field, significantly accelerating the process. AI modules and software developed within the GRAPHIA project will be available as open-source resources, allowing reuse by the SSH community and other organizations. Citation data will be provided in an open format, increasing its accessibility and potential for reuse. The LUMEN project will establish a multi-domain resource discovery platform, facilitating researchers' access to publications, data, and software across various fields. LUMEN will integrate publication and author metrics, enriching the OpenCitations ecosystem with data from new scientific domains. Users of LUMEN platforms will have access to standardized controlled vocabularies, ontologies, and taxonomies to enhance resource discovery. The projects will enhance the visibility and accessibility of SSH data by constructing a cohesive semantic information space.

Conclusion

The extraction of citation data from SSH publications within the GRAPHIA and LUMEN projects, leveraging OpenCitations' expertise, is crucial for advancing open science in SSH. These efforts will enhance OPERAS Metrics Service and SSH KG by providing high-quality citation data, improving interoperability and visibility of research resources, and granting the SSH community access to innovative tools and data. The projects will ensure access to standardized controlled vocabularies, ontologies, and taxonomic classifications. Ultimately, these initiatives will accelerate knowledge discovery and support researchers in SSH and beyond.

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